

Knowledge, Perception, and Use of Vape Among the Saudi Population in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Vaping has emerged as a significant trend within the broader context of global tobacco use, posing new public health challenges. **Aim:** To assess the knowledge, perception, and use of vaping among the Saudi population in Riyadh. **Methodology:** A cross-sectional analytic study design, conducted from September 2023 to May 2024, involved 353 participants selected through a convenience sampling technique. Data collection was facilitated via a self-administered structured questionnaire adapted from the CDC and translated into Arabic, focusing on sociodemographic information, vaping knowledge, perceptions, and usage patterns. **Results:** The results indicated a vaping prevalence of 31.20%. A majority of participants (79.09%) displayed good overall knowledge, though this association was not statistically significant ($X^2=2.066$, $P=0.3559$). Vapers tended to have a neutral perception of vaping (55.45%), with this association being statistically significant ($X^2=17.238$, $P=0.0002$). **Conclusion:** The study revealed that 31% of participants are vape users with good knowledge about vaping's components, health risks, benefits of quitting, and regulations. However, their perception was neutral, viewing vaping as less harmful, less addictive, and less expensive than conventional cigarettes, and potentially assisting both in quitting and starting smoking. **Recommendations:** There is a need to develop educational programs targeting individuals aged 18 to 22 to address misconceptions and highlight the detrimental effects of vaping, aiming to shift perceptions and reduce its prevalence in this age group.

Introduction

Vaping involves a variety of battery-powered devices, including e-cigarettes, vape pens, and ENDS, which heat a liquid to create an inhaled aerosol [1]. As of February 2020, the CDC reported over 2,800 hospitalizations due to EVALI, with 68 deaths [2]. Global vaping prevalence

has risen, with 58 million vapers in 2018, expected to reach 68 million by 2020 [3]. In Saudi Arabia, 3.9% of adults used e-cigarettes in 2019, with usage varying by age group, particularly high among those aged 18-24 (66.9%) [4-5]. Vaping is less harmful than smoking but still poses physical risks, including EVALI and

More Information

How to cite this article: Alluhaidan R, Babutain A, Alharbi M, Fiala L. Knowledge, Perception, and Use of Vape Among the Saudi Population in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(4):4-13.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(4).01

Keywords:

Vaping,
knowledge,
perception,
Riyadh,
Saudi Arabia

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cardiovascular issues such as increased heart rate and high blood pressure [6-7,8]. Nicotine in vapes can cause addiction, depression, anxiety, and increase the likelihood of smoking conventional cigarettes [9-8]. Environmental concerns include pollution from the production and disposal of vaping products, which contribute to electronic waste and toxic chemical release [10]. Vaping is particularly harmful to vulnerable groups such as adolescents, pregnant women, and developing fetuses [11-12]. Various factors influence vaping, including age, gender, social environment, and perceptions of e-cigarettes as less harmful and helpful for quitting smoking cigarettes [13-14]. Adolescents are influenced by peers and the availability of flavored e-cigarettes, viewing them as modern and socially acceptable [15-16].

Materials and Methods

This cross-sectional analytic study was conducted from September 2023 to May 2024, on Saudi citizens in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used to recruit the participants.

The sample size was calculated by the software application "n4studies" [17]. The study design is cross-sectional, and the target population is more than ten thousand. Therefore, the formula for calculating the sample size for an infinite population proportion was used:

$$n = \frac{z_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^2 p(1-p)}{d^2} \quad (1)$$

n = desired sample size, Z = standard normal deviation, usually set at 1.96, which corresponds to a 95% confidence limit, α = alpha sample = 0.05, p = proportion of vaping among adults in Saudi Arabia = 33.6% (18), d = degree of accuracy, usually set at the 0.05 level, Design effect = 1. This provides a sample size of 343 participants.

The study questionnaire was adapted from a CDC questionnaire on vape use and then translated into Arabic for effective use by the Saudi participants [19]. A digital version of the questionnaire was developed using Google Forms and shared with Saudi participants via social media platforms including WhatsApp, X (the new name of Twitter), Snapchat, and Telegram.

The questionnaire consists of four sections. The first section is about sociodemographic data, including nationality, residence, age, gender, educational level, occupation, and marital status. The second section is about knowledge of vaping (18 questions). The responses to questions are in the form of yes, no, and I don't know. The correct answer was scored 1, the incorrect and I do not know answers were scored 0, even the reverse questions (three questions). There is an open question regarding the legal age for purchasing

vapes, which is under 18, and the answer is coded as correct or incorrect. The score for this open question is combined with the other questions (there is a specific prohibited age to purchase vape in Saudi Arabia). If a participant answers both questions correctly, they receive a score of 1. The total score for knowledge of vaping is 17. The percentile is used to categorize participants' knowledge into good, moderate, and poor categories. 75% and more of the total vape knowledge score (13 and more) are categorized as good knowledge, while 50% to less than 75% of the total score (8 to 12) are categorized as moderate knowledge. Lastly, those with less than 50% knowledge score (less than 8) are categorized as poor knowledge. The third section of the questionnaire is about perceptions of vaping (five questions). The questions were in the form of a five-point Likert scale and were scored (strongly disagree, scored 1; disagree, scored 2; neutral, scored 3; agree, scored 4; strongly agree, scored 5). The total score for the perception of vaping is 25. The maximum possible score is used to categorize participants' perceptions into positive, neutral, and negative categories. The maximum score is 25 and the minimum score is 5. The numbers between maximum and minimum score are divided into three and it is equal to a range of each level. Therefore, 19 or more of the total score is categorized as positive perception, while 12 to 18 of the total score is categorized as neutral perception. Lastly, those with 5 to 11 of the total score were categorized as negative perceptions. The fourth section of the questionnaire is about vape use and covers 11 questions, including the ever use of vape, which combines those who have tried it before with current users. Other questions are exclusive to current users, including the age of started vaping, vaping in front of other people, vaping in public places, duration of vaping, daily use of vape, number of puffs per session, smoking status, time of vaping, and awareness of the warnings on the vape package. Last question, where to purchase vape which is in the form of multiple-choice. The questions were presented as tables and graphs. Furthermore, there were two multiple-choice questions among vapers. The participant could select more than one answer. The first question asked about factors that might cause someone to vape among vapers. The second question asked about vaping by surrounding people among vapers. The questions were presented as graphs. The data was collected after approval by the institutional review board (IRB) at Princess Nourah Bint Abdulrahman University. A clear explanation was provided to the participants on the first page of the electronic survey. The participants were informed about the aim of the study, voluntary participation, and withdrawal from the study without any consequences. In addition, the anonymity of participants was

maintained, and the data was used only for research purposes without disclosing personal data. All participants were asked to give their informed consent to join the study by answering the questionnaire.

Selection and Description of Participants

The study participants included males and females of all ages who are Saudi citizens residing in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Technical Information

The research aims to achieve the following objectives. First, to assess the prevalence of vape use among the Saudi population in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Second, to assess the level of knowledge and perception regarding the use of vape among the Saudi population in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Third, to assess the relationship between knowledge, perception, and the use of vape among the Saudi population in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Statistics

Statistical analysis was performed using the software JMP version 17 [20]. Frequency tables and graphs were used for descriptive data. In addition, analytic statistics were done by calculating the P-value and the Chi-square test to assess the relationships between knowledge, perception, and use of vape. P-value<0.05 is considered statistically significant.

Results

Figure (1) shows the participants' knowledge about vape components. The majority of participants answered "yes" (Correct answer) that vape consists of flavors (92.07%). While 3.68% of participants answered "yes" it consists of vitamins (Incorrect answer) and almost 30% of them answered "I don't know" (Shortage of knowledge).

Figure 1: Participants' Knowledge about Vape Components

Figure (2) demonstrates the participants' knowledge about the health risks of vaping. Most participants answered "yes" correctly that vaping can cause nicotine addiction (85.84%), lung problems (94.62%), heart problems (87.82%), cancer (84.99%), and explosions from vaping devices (75.07%). Additionally, the least portion of the group (8.78%) answered "yes" that there are no health risks (Incorrect answer).

Figure 2: Participants' Knowledge about the Health Risks of Vaping

Figure (3) demonstrates the participants' use of vape (N=353). It shows that 68.80% of the participants do not use vape while 31.20% use vape.

Figure 3: Use of Vape

Figure 4: Reasons for Vaping among Vapers

Figure (4) demonstrates the reasons for vaping among vapers (N=110). The majority of vapers' reason is to quit smoking (67.30%), while only 24.50% of vapers' reason

it's cheaper than other products. Additionally, it was found that 65.50% of vapers' reason is to socialize with friends and a variety of flavors.

Figure 5: Vaping by Surrounding People among Vapers

Figure (5) demonstrates vaping by surrounding people among vapers (N=110). It was found that friends have the highest percentage of vaping by close people (80.9%), while mothers have the lowest percentage of vaping by close people (3.6%).

Figure 6: The Source of Vape among Vapers

Figure (6) demonstrates the source of vape among vapers (N=38). The majority of vapers got their vape from vape shops (94.70%), while the minority got it from their families (2.60%). Additionally, it was found that 13.20% of vapers got their vape from supermarkets and grocery stores.

Figure (7) demonstrates the timing of vape use among vapers (N=38). The majority of the vapers used vape when gathering with friends, got stressed (73.70% for both of them), or were bored (68.40%), while 60.50% of the vapers used vape at any time.

Figure 7: Timing of Vape Use among Vapers

Table (1) represents the distribution of sociodemographic characteristics among the sample population (N=353). Most of the study participants were in the age group 18 to 22 years old (51.84%), females (78.47%), of bachelor's and postgraduate degrees (59.21%), with non-health background study (52.12%), being students as an occupation (61.47%), and of single marital status (77.90%).

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of the Study Participants

	N (353)	(%)
Age		
13 to 17	29	8.22
18 to 22	183	51.84
23 to 27	55	15.58
28 to 32	28	7.93
33 to 37	17	4.82
38 and more	41	11.61
Gender		
Female	277	78.47
Male	76	21.53
Educational level		
Middle school	9	2.55
High school	90	25.50
Diploma degree	45	12.75
Bachelor's and postgraduate degree	209	59.21
Background study		
Health	169	47.88

Non-health	184	52.12
Occupation		
Student	217	61.47
Employed outside home	93	26.35
Self-employed	6	1.70
Housewife	15	4.25
Unemployed	22	6.23
Marital status		
Single	275	77.90
Married	73	20.68
Divorced or separated	5	1.42

Table (2) represents the participants' knowledge about the benefits of quitting vape use. Most participants answered "yes" correctly that quitting vape reduces adverse effects on the body (88.95%), reduces stress

and increases physical activity (79.60% for both of them), and saves money (88.10%). Additionally, 6.23% answered "yes" quitting vaping has no benefit (Incorrect answer).

Table 2: Participants' Knowledge about the Benefits of Quitting Vape Use

Benefits of quitting vaping	Yes N (%)	No N (%)	I don't know N (%)
Reduces adverse effects on the body	314 (88.95)	26 (7.37)	13 (3.68)
Reduces stress and anxiety	281 (79.60)	40 (11.33)	32 (9.07)
Saves money	311 (88.10)	35 (9.92)	7 (1.98)
Increases physical activity	281 (79.60)	40 (11.33)	32 (9.07)
Quitting vaping has no benefit	22 (6.23)	310 (87.82)	21 (5.95)

Table (3) represents the participants' knowledge of the regulations in Saudi Arabia regarding the age of vape purchase. Most participants answered "yes" correctly

regarding the specific prohibited age to purchase vape in Saudi Arabia (49.86%), while 40.23% of participants wrote the correct age.

Table 3: Knowledge of the Regulations in Saudi Arabia Regarding the Age of Vape Purchase

		N (%)
The specific prohibited age to purchase vape in Saudi Arabia	Yes	176 (49.86)
	No	52 (14.73)
	I don't know	125 (35.41)
The age number which is prohibited to purchase vape	Correct age	142 (40.23)
	Incorrect age	44 (12.46)
	I don't know	167 (47.31)

Table (4) represents the participants' perceptions towards vape use. It was found that 53.64% of the vapers agreed that is less addictive than the conventional cigarette, and agreed that vaping helps smokers quit smoking and helps to start smoking

conventional cigarettes (50% and 43.64% respectively) (Positive perception). At the same time, 44.44% of non-vapers disagreed that vaping is less harmful than conventional cigarettes (Negative perception).

Table 4: Participants' Perception towards Vape Use

		Vape use	
		Yes N (Column %)	No N (Column %)
Vaping is less harmful than conventional cigarette	Agree	56 (50.91)	58 (23.87)
	Neutral	29 (26.36)	77 (31.69)
	Disagree	25 (22.73)	108 (44.44)
Vaping is less expensive than the conventional cigarette	Agree	52 (47.27)	74 (30.45)
	Neutral	29 (26.36)	120 (49.38)

	Disagree	29 (26.36)	49 (20.16)
Vaping is less addictive than the conventional cigarette	Agree	59 (53.64)	61 (25.10)
	Neutral	21 (19.09)	98 (40.33)
	Disagree	30 (27.27)	84 (34.57)
Vaping helps smokers quit smoking	Agree	55 (50)	60 (24.69)
	Neutral	24 (21.82)	72 (29.63)
	Disagree	31 (28.18)	111 (45.68)
Vaping helps to start smoking conventional cigarettes	Agree	48 (43.64)	142 (58.44)
	Neutral	34 (30.91)	76 (31.28)
	Disagree	28 (25.45)	25 (10.29)

Table (5) shows the pattern of vape use among vapers. The majority of vapers don't smoke conventional cigarettes with vape (55.26%), vape more than two years (68.42%), vape more than seven times per day

(63.16%), taking more than 16 puffs per session (47.37%), vape in public and in front of others (63.16% and 73.68% respectively), and read health warnings on vape packages (55.26%).

Table 5: Patterns of Vape Use among Vapers

		N (38)	%
Smoking conventional cigarettes with vape	Yes	17	44.74
	No	21	55.26
Duration of vaping	Less than two years	12	31.58
	More than two years	26	68.42
The number of vaping per day	Once or less	7	18.42
	2-4 times	2	5.26
	5-7 times	5	13.16
	More than 7 times	24	63.16
The number of puffs taken from a vape during one session.	1-5 puffs	8	21.05
	6-10 puffs	7	18.42
	11-15 puffs	5	13.16
	More than 16 puffs	18	47.37
Use of vape in public places	Yes	24	63.16
	No	14	36.84
Use of vape in front of other people	Yes	28	73.68
	No	10	26.32
Reading the health warnings on the front and back of the vape package	Yes	21	55.26
	No	17	44.74

Table (6) shows the relationship between knowledge, perception, and vape use. It shows that vapers had a neutral perception about vape (55.45%). This association is statistically significant ($\chi^2=17.238$,

$P=0.0002$). At the same time, it was found that vapers had good knowledge about vape (79.09%), but this association is statistically not significant ($\chi^2= 2.066$, $P= 0.3559$).

Table 6: Relationship between Knowledge, Perception, and Vape Use

Perception categories	Vape use			Chi-Square test
	Yes N (Column %)	No N (Column %)	Total	
Positive perception	41 (37.27)	44 (18.11)	85	$\chi^2= 17.238$ $P= 0.0002^*$
Neutral perception	61 (55.45)	160 (65.84)	221	
Negative perception	8 (7.27)	39 (16.05)	47	
Total	110	243	353	
Knowledge categories	Vape use			Chi-Square test
	Yes N (Column %)	No N (Column %)	Total	
Good knowledge	87 (79.09)	182 (74.90)	269	$\chi^2= 2.066$

Moderate knowledge	18 (16.36)	54 (22.22)	72	P= 0.3559
Poor knowledge	5 (4.55)	7 (2.88)	12	
Total	110	243	353	

Note: *Statistically significant (p<0.05)

Table (7) represents the association between sociodemographic characteristics and vape use. It was found that the highest percentage who use vape from age 18 to 22 (45.45%), female (54.55%), have a bachelor’s and postgraduate degree (62.73%), with non-health background study (60%), were employed or student (45.45% for both of them), and single marital status (77.27%). There is a statistically significant

association between vape use and age ($X^2= 24.728$, $P= 0.0002$), educational level ($X^2= 12.805$, $P= 0.0051$), background study ($X^2= 3.971$, $P= 0.0463$), while there is a high statistically significant association between vape use and gender ($X^2= 54.139$, $P= <.0001$), and occupation ($X^2= 35.051$, $P= <.0001$). At the same time, there is no association between vape use and marital status ($X^2= 0.187$, $P= 0.9110$).

Table 7: Relationship between Sociodemographic Characteristics and Vape Use

Sociodemographic characteristics	Vape use			Chi-Square test
	Yes N (Column %)	No N (Column %)	Total	
Age group:				
13 to 17	3 (2.73)	26 (10.70)	29	$X^2= 24.728$ $P= 0.0002^*$
18 to 22	50 (45.45)	133 (54.73)	183	
23 to 27	21 (19.09)	34 (13.99)	55	
28 to 32	15 (13.64)	13 (5.35)	28	
33 to 37	11 (10)	6 (2.47)	17	
38 and more	10 (9.09)	31 (12.76)	41	
Total	110	243	353	
Gender				
Female	60 (54.55)	217 (89.3)	277	$X^2= 54.139$ $P= <.0001^{**}$
Male	50 (45.45)	26 (10.7)	76	
Total	110	243	353	
Educational level				
Middle school	0	9 (3.70)	9	$X^2= 12.805$ $P= 0.0051^*$
High school	20 (18.18)	70 (28.81)	90	
Diploma degree	21 (19.09)	24 (9.88)	45	
Bachelor’s and postgraduate degree	69 (62.73)	140 (57.61)	209	
Total	110	243	353	
Background study				
Health	44 (40)	125 (51.44)	169	$X^2= 3.971$ $P= 0.0463^*$
Non-health	66 (60)	118 (48.56)	184	
Total	110	243	353	
Occupation				
Student	50 (45.45)	167 (68.72)	217	$X^2= 35.051$ $P= <.0001^{**}$
Employed	50 (45.45)	43 (17.7)	93	
Self-employed	4 (3.64)	2 (0.82)	6	
Housewife	2 (1.82)	13 (5.35)	15	
Unemployed	4 (3.64)	18 (7.41)	22	
Total	110	243	353	
Marital status				
Single	85 (77.27)	190 (78.19)	275	$X^2= 0.187$ $P= 0.9110$
Married	23 (20.91)	50 (20.58)	73	
Divorced or separated	2 (1.82)	3 (1.23)	5	
Total	110	243	353	

Note: *Statistically significant (p<0.05); **High statistically significant (p= <.0001)

Discussion

The current study found a vaping prevalence of 31.20%, which aligns with another study conducted among Saudis in Saudi Arabia (2022), where the prevalence was reported to be 26.3% [5]. Similarities in these regions' demographics or social factors could explain the comparable vaping rates.

The current study shows that the participants knew that vape consists of nicotine (84.70%). Compared with another study conducted in Lebanon (2020) where the participants knew the vape consists of nicotine (61.1%) [21]. The current study also found that the participants knew that vaping could lead to nicotine addiction (85.84%) (Figure 2). This reflects with another study done in Saudi Arabia among adolescents and adults (2023), where participants knew vaping was addictive (38.20%) [22]. This knowledge may be attributed to areas for improvement in public awareness of vaping-related these issues. Suggests that educational efforts have been somewhat effective, especially when considering the higher percentages in the current study compared to previous studies. However, knowledge gaps still exist in the current study. For example, 30.03% weren't aware that vaping doesn't contain vitamins, and 19.26% didn't know burns are a potential vaping risk. More educational interventions are crucial among vapers and non-vapers are well-informed. Furthermore, it was found in the current study the participants knew the correct age that prohibited them from purchasing the vape in Saudi Arabia which is less than 18 (40.23%). This aligns with another study done in Jeddah among Saudi population (2024) where around (44.5%) knew the correct age restriction [23]. Furthermore, the current study showed that vape users had good knowledge about vaping (79.09%), but this association was not statistically significant ($X^2= 2.066$, $P= 0.3559$). In contrast, a study conducted in Saudi Arabia (2020) revealed that nearly half of the participants exhibited poor knowledge, with a high proportion unable to recognize the health hazards of vaping [18]. These findings underscore the variability in knowledge levels observed across different studies. Overall, while the current study indicates a generally good level of knowledge about vaping among participants, the lack of a significant association with vaping behavior suggests that other factors may play a more significant role in influencing individuals' decisions regarding vaping. This highlights the importance of continued education and awareness campaigns.

The findings of the current study revealed that the majority of vape users agreed that vaping helps in smoking cessation, is less harmful, and is less addictive than conventional cigarettes (50%, 50.91%, and 53.64% respectively). A study conducted at Taibah University

(2020) found that the majority of vape users agreed that vaping helps in smoking cessation, is less harmful, and is less addictive than conventional cigarettes (43.9%, 57%, and 52.6% respectively) [14]. This agreement may be attributed to the absence of burning tobacco, which produces harmful chemicals. Vaping products are often marketed as smoking cessation aids or as safer alternatives to traditional cigarettes. This messaging can influence people's perceptions and lead them to believe that vaping is a better option for quitting smoking or reducing harm. Some participants may have personally experienced positive outcomes from using vaping products to quit smoking or reduce their tobacco consumption.

On the other hand, the majority of non-vapers disagree that vaping helps with smoking cessation and is less harmful than conventional cigarettes (45.68% and 44.44%, respectively). Similarly, at Taibah University, non-vapers disagree that vaping helps with smoking cessation and is less harmful than conventional cigarettes (41.1% and 45.9%, respectively) [14]. This disagreement might be attributed to non-vapers being influenced by public health campaigns and media reports highlighting the potential risks and unknown long-term effects of vaping.

According to practice in the current study, the vapers showed that they had used vape for more than two years (68.42%). Compared to a previous study at King Saud University in Al-Ahsa (2022), it was found that the participants used vaping for more than two years (31.69%) [24]. This upward trend in prolonged vaping habits may reflect evolving societal attitudes towards vaping, increased availability of vaping products, and potential normalization of vaping behavior over time. There are some limitations in this study. Firstly, the sampling technique is the non-probability sample technique (convenience sample), which limits our ability to generalize the findings to a larger population. Secondly, despite the survey being sent widely, finding responses from men in the survey was challenging, resulting in a significantly limited timeframe for collecting and analyzing data.

Conclusion

The study revealed that 31% of participants are vape users. The participants had good knowledge about vaping including its components, health risks, benefits of quitting, and regulations. However, their perception was neutral towards vaping in these statements that include less harmful, less addictive, and less expensive compared to conventional cigarettes, and potentially assisting both in quitting and starting smoking.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to express their gratitude to everyone who participated in this research project. This includes the participants who generously completed

the questionnaire, as well as healthcare professionals who provided invaluable insights during the validity review. We would like to thank our supervisor, Prof. Lamiaa Fiala, for her guidance and support. Her expertise and patience were invaluable to us, and we are grateful for her willingness to share her knowledge and time with us. We also extend our thanks to our instructors, Dr. Huny Bakry and Dr. Samira Mahboub, for their encouragement, feedback, and support throughout this project.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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